

SWISS AIR POLLUTION EXPOSURE MAPS

Documentation

Kees de Hoogh
Benjamin Flückiger

1. INPUT DATA AND MODELLING FRAMEWORK

Air pollution models were developed using routinely available measurement station data combined with a comprehensive set of spatiotemporal predictor variables, including land use, traffic indicators, population density, elevation, satellite-derived NO₂, aerosol optical depth (AOD), and NDVI, and meteorological variables. Detailed descriptions are published for each pollutant:

- ❖ *De Hoogh, Kees, et al. "Predicting fine-scale daily NO₂ for 2005–2016 incorporating OMI satellite data across Switzerland." *Environmental science & technology* 53.17 (2019): 10279-10287.*
- ❖ *De Hoogh, Kees, et al. "Modelling daily PM_{2.5} concentrations at high spatio-temporal resolution across Switzerland." *Environmental Pollution* 233 (2018): 1147-1154.*

2. OUTPUTS

The main outputs are Swiss-wide exposure maps for multiple air pollutants, produced as high-resolution geospatial datasets for each day/year as geotiff files.

NO₂ was modelled from 01.01.2005 to 31.12.2024

PM_{2.5} was modelled from 01.01.2003 to 31.12.2024

Approximate data volumes for the daily surfaces are:

NO₂: ~160 GB

PM_{2.5}: ~180 GB

3. DATA ACCESS

Due to data volume and licensing considerations, the exposure maps and associated datasets are not distributed directly via Zenodo. Access is provided upon request. Please contact Swiss TPH through one of the following email addresses:

Benjamin.flueckiger@swisstph.ch

C.dehoogh@swisstph.ch

Martin.roosli@swisstph.ch